

Advanced 3D EM Simulation Environment for Development, Testing, and Usage of Medical Microwave Imaging Devices

Branko Kolundzija, Marija Nikolic Stevanovic, Mladjen Stevanetic, Branislav Ninkovic, and Tushar Singh

Abstract — Recently, microwave imaging has been envisioned as an important complimentary tool in medical diagnostics, besides golden standards in this field, such as CT scan and MRI. However, in order to achieve performances that qualify this technology to be translated from research bench to patient bedside, we need advanced 3D EM simulation environment. As a base for such environment we started from commercial, general purpose 3D EM solver WIPL-D Pro and its CAD variant. In addition, we added libraries of a) tissue properties, b) antenna models c) models of the antenna arrays/systems, d) models of parts of human body (phantoms), and e) scenarios that combine antennas and phantoms to emulate practical usage of microwave imaging devices. Special procedures/new options are developed to enable easy creation and fast and accurate analysis of new libraries' components. The effectiveness of such 3D EM simulation environment will be illustrated on a number of practical examples.

Keywords — 3D EM Simulation, Microwave Imaging

I. INTRODUCTION

In the past decade, there has been a continuous interest in research, developing and testing of the microwave imaging devices in medical diagnostic and monitoring (e.g. for the breast-cancer detection [1], bone imaging, stroke detection, [2], etc.). Although this technology is still far beyond the level at which it can be used in clinical practice, its potentials regarding the cost-effectiveness and portability are widely recognize when compared to the conventional technologies such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and computed tomography (CT). In order to achieve performances that qualify microwave imaging systems to approach the patient bedside, we need advanced 3D EM simulation environment.

In this paper we propose an efficient and flexible 3D EM simulation environment for developing, testing, and using of medical microwave imaging devices. Section II describes the structure of such environment. Section III gives basic

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information about WIPL-D software and reasons for choosing of this solver for a base of 3D simulation environment. Section IV presents the libraries of 3D models of antennas, tissues, phantoms, antenna systems and scenarios related to microwave imaging in medical applications. Section V elaborates procedures/options/tools for creation of new elements, their inclusion into libraries, and their composition into systems/scenarios. Section VI gives typical example of microwave imaging scenario.

II. STRUCTURE OF THE 3D ELECTROMAGNETIC SIMULATION ENVIRONMENT

General purpose 3D EM simulation software WIPL-D Pro and its CAD variant are used as a base of 3D EM simulation environment for development testing and usage of medical microwave imaging devices [3].

These, general purpose 3D EM solvers, are supplemented with libraries of relevant components: a) human tissues' properties, b) models of human bodies or their parts (phantoms), c) models of canonical and real life antennas, d) antenna arrays, systems and templates of predefined antenna arrangements and microwave imaging scenarios.

Besides libraries, this environment also includes special procedures/options/tools that allow users to create their own unique components, to include those components into libraries, and to compose the library components into particular scenarios. In particular, this environment can support functioning of the microwave imaging devices if it is augmented by appropriate set of microwave imaging algorithms.

III. BASE: GENERAL PURPOSE 3D EM SOLVER

WIPL-D Pro 3D EM simulation solver is general purpose 3D EM modeling software, which basically performs simulation in frequency domain. The structure to be simulated is in general case composed of homogeneous, isotropic and linear parts (domains) of arbitrary complex-valued permittivity and permeability. Using not only real, but also complex values for material EM properties enables characterization not only lossless, but also lossy materials. In particular, these parts can be made of perfect electric conductors (PECs). Real metallic materials with skin effect losses are taken into account by using model of distributing

loadings. Other types of distributed loading can be used to modify the nature of PEC in different ways, e.g. to load it capacitively or inductively. Such defined structure can be excited in many ways, by plane waves, delta and point generators, field generators, currents generators, and various types of guiding waves (wave ports).

Full wave analysis of such arbitrarily defined structures is performed by solving Surface Integral Equations (SIEs) using Method of Moments (MoM) [4,5]. The flexibility of geometrical modeling is achieved using two types of building elements: right truncated cones for metallic wires and bilinear surfaces (quadrilateral patches defined by 4 nodes arbitrarily placed in the space) for metallic and dielectric/metallic surfaces. In particular, special care is devoted to wire-to-plate junctions, protrusion of wires through dielectric surfaces, and composite metallic and dielectric junctions.

Efficiency of EM modeling and simulation is at the first place achieved using higher order bases instead of most often used low order ones. Thus, while usage of low order RWG bases over triangles (of maximum patch size of 0.1λ) requires 300 unknowns per λ^2 [6], higher order bases can reduce this number for an order of magnitude (30 unknowns per λ^2) or even more. On the other hand from the hardware point of view the acceleration of one to two orders of magnitude can be achieved using parallelization on multiple CPUs and Graphic processors units (GPUs) [7].

IV. LIBRARIES OF RELEVANT COMPONENTS

The role of the library is to contain a large number of both typical and narrowly specialized elements that could be used in the development of medical microwave imaging devices that should be tested. Libraries should allow easier access to previously created elements and accelerate the development of individual projects. Libraries includes different element types:

A. Tissues

Knowledge of dielectric properties of tissues at different frequencies is of great importance for researchers and practitioners in this field. To accommodate that WIPL-D created a frequency dependent, dielectric properties table that is based on work presented in [8]. Each of the tissues listed in that table (blood, bone (cancellous), bone (cortical), brain (grey matter), brain (white matter), fat (infiltrated), fat (not infiltrated), heart, kidney, lens cortex, liver, ling (inflated), muscle, skin (dry), skin (wet), spleen, tendon) is defined by the values for electrical conductivity and the real and imaginary part of relative permittivity. These values are modeled at an experimental spectrum from 10 Hz to 100 GHz, using widely accepted Cole-Cole relaxation as

$$\hat{\epsilon}(\omega) = \epsilon_{\infty} + \frac{\Delta\epsilon}{1+(j\omega\tau)^{1-\alpha}} \quad (1)$$

Where $\hat{\epsilon}$ is a complex dielectric constants. The magnitude of the dispersion is described as $\Delta\epsilon = \epsilon_s - \epsilon_{\infty}$, with ϵ_s and ϵ_{∞} being “static“ and “infinite“ frequency dielectric constants. ω is the angular frequency, τ is a time constant and α is the exponent parameter, which takes a value between 0 and 1.

B. Phantoms

Phantoms play an important part in the design and testing of hardware and software of microwave imaging systems. In order to study the interaction between the human tissues and EM waves, many phantoms have been developed [9]-[11].

Realistic (real-life) phantom models are obtained by importing their structures from CAD files of various formats and assigning tissue properties. In addition to most standard CAD files/formats like Parasolid, IGES, STEP, CATIA, AutoCAD, etc., there are files/format of special interest for medical applications and microwave imaging, STL and Voxel.

Beside those realistic phantoms, three other types of phantoms are included in our library. First of them are canonical phantoms. Canonical phantoms are mostly made from basic geometric bodies or combinations of them (spheres, ellipsoids, cylinders, etc.), of such dimensions that they roughly represent certain human organs and body parts.

For the experimental purposes, researchers try to fabricate phantoms that encompassed the most important parts of realistic phantom with less important details neglected. The complexity of such phantoms is between the canonical and realistic. In what follows such phantoms will be referred to as fabricated phantoms.

Mixed phantoms represent combinations of realistic, canonical and fabricated phantoms, where different phantom parts are taken from different phantom types.

Fig. 1 shows various phantom models.

Fig. 1. Phantoms: a) canonical model (head + brain + stroke), b) mixed model (realistic head + canonical brain + stroke), c) mixed model (simplified head + realistic brain + stroke).

C. Antennas

Realistic antenna models can be either created from the scratch in the CAD editor, or imported from the CAD files. In this work we started from classification of antennas used for medical applications presented in paper [12]. As we encounter new work on medical microwave imaging, we discover new types or designs of antennas used by researchers in this field and strive to add them to our library. The idea is that after certain time various antenna types used for different medical applications would be included into this library.

However for the fast checking which type of the antenna would be optimal for the specific imaging system it is convenient to pick up one of the canonical models (Dipole antennas, Yagi antenna, Vivaldi antenna, Open-waveguide antenna, etc.). Examples of canonical antennas, open-waveguide and Vivaldi antenna, are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Canonical model of open waveguide antenna with T-probe (left) and realistic model of Vivaldi antenna (right).

D. Antenna arrays/systems, microwave imaging scenarios

Once we have 3D EM models of antennas and phantoms of interest, we can easily compose them into antenna arrays, antenna systems and microwave imaging scenarios, by importing the elements into the main project, and moving them to the desired position and rotating them to the desired orientation. Libraries of such typical compositions are valuable for designers of new systems.

V. PROCEDURE/TOOLS FOR CREATION OF LIBRARY ELEMENTS AND THEIR COMPOSITION INTO SCENARIOS

As mentioned previously both realistic antennas and phantoms can be obtained by importing from standard CAD files. The imported structure is saved in the Parasolid format, and all further actions in refining the model are performed in the Parasolid format. Generally, the advantage of standard CAD formats is that various, even very complex, shapes are represented by relatively small number of faces, which are then optimally meshed into bilinear surfaces. However this procedure is not convenient in the case of STL files, in which even simple shapes are defined using many triangles. After importing the STL triangles are translated into the Parasolid faces. Thus obtained huge set of faces can not be easily manipulated (translated, rotated, scaled, etc.) and meshing of the set results in high number of quadrilaterals and unknowns. On the other hand Voxel files cannot be automatically translated to the Parasolid format. Hence, special software tools are developed for handling Voxel and STL files.

Voxel files are generated combining geometrical data obtained by CT or MRI with measured tissue properties. These files give information in a dense grid of points about tissue-types as well as electrical properties. After reading Voxel files, tiny cubes are defined surrounding each voxel, i.e. voxels are positioned in centers of these cubes. Extending the values corresponding to the voxel into small cubes and eliminating the air filled cubes allow us to work with 3D structures that can be simulated. However, the initial number of voxel cubes is usually extremely high requiring huge resources for simulation. Hence, special algorithm is developed to reduce the complexity of the model: the initial model is subdivided into groups of $n \times n \times n$ voxel cubes; each group is merged into single homogeneous cube with averaged material property; averaging is performed using various "mixing formulas" (i.e. formulas for calculation of average electrical properties of material mixtures); the reduction can be maximized by optimal choice of mixing formula and their parameters. For example, in the case of a breast models having $\sim 250^3$ voxels, acceptable results for near field distribution inside and around the breast can be obtained even by choosing $n = 24$. Fig. 3 shows models with $n = 6, 24$.

Fig. 3. Voxel model, when parameter "n" is set to 6 (left) and 24 (right)

It should be noted that even after such huge reduction the resulting model contains few thousands square surfaces. If imported to the CAD editor the manipulations of such model would be relatively slow. Hence, the presentation of such model, as well as manipulations and further refinement is performed in the fast classic editor.

The classic editor is also adjusted for presentation, manipulation, refinement, and meshing of STL files. A number of refinement options are developed: deleting unnecessary parts, filling the holes, decimation, etc. Also, in-house mesher is developed to transform the triangular mesh into a quadrilateral mesh into three steps: a) triangles are merged into quadrilaterals, b) pairs of nearest orphan triangles together with in between quads are remerged into quadrilaterals only, and c) quadrilaterals of low shape quality factor are combined with neighboring quadrilaterals into hexagons, and re-meshed with increased shape quality factor. Fig. 4. shows the STL model of the white matter of a brain before and after meshing.

There are few steps to be taken in the scenario creation process. The first step is to select the elements to be used in the scenario: phantoms and antennas. It involves creating brand new phantoms and/or antennas or using pre-made ones.

Fig. 4. Previewed models of white matter of a brain: triangular STL model (left) and quadrilateral model (right)

There are few steps to be taken in the scenario creation process. The first step is to select the elements to be used in the scenario: phantoms and antennas. It involves creating brand new phantoms and/or antennas or using pre-made ones.

The next step is to make decision about the matching medium between the phantom and antennas. Matching medium represents the material that can surround the phantom or certain its part, as well as antennas. In real life scenario, matching medium would be a helmet or part of a wardrobe, made from special material and including antennas in its structure. The role of this medium is to mitigate the reflections that occur on the outer surface of the body under test. For different parts of the body, due to different material characteristics, different matching medium parameters are used. The next step is to adjust the antennas to be matched in the presence of this material.

Final step in creation of a scenario involves choosing the number of antennas and deciding on their position and orientation around the phantom. This task can be further facilitated by creating the template which defines the antenna positions and orientations by a set of successive translations and rotations. In this case the chosen antenna can be automatically multiplied, and each copy positioned and oriented. Fig. 5. shows two microwave imaging scenarios for diagnosis of a stroke placed at the brain boundary, combining phantoms from Fig. 1 and antennas from Fig. 2.

Fig. 5. Microwave imaging scenarios for diagnosis of a stroke placed at the brain boundary: a) Mixed phantom with open-waveguide antennas, and b) Mixed phantom with Vivaldi antennas.

VI. NUMERICAL RESULTS

Regarding the inverse scattering algorithms, the electromagnetic solvers yield two types of data that are used for imaging. The first set of data is the scattering parameter matrix, data measured by antenna systems placed around the body. The other set are the values of the electric field vector

inside the phantom. Fig. 6 shows that near field distribution inside and outside, at the first glance, quite different phantoms from Fig. 1, are very similar. Does it mean that different heads like these two can be used instead of prime head for various patients, which would facilitate the diagnostics. This is the question that could be answered by using advanced 3D EM simulation environment elaborated in this paper.

Fig. 6. Near field distribution at the horizontal cross section near the stroke position for the phantoms from Fig. 2.

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